

ECONOMIC IMPACT OF ATT ON PATIENTS AND THEIR FAMILIES - A Cross-Sectional Study in Gulab Devi Hospital Lahore

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Abstract

Background: In order to inform the development of different strategies needed to deal with the alarming economic impact on TB patients, a study was conducted to assess the economic impact of TB on patients and their families belonging from the urban, peri urban and rural areas in Gulab Devi hospital, Lahore, Pakistan.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was done in Gulab Devi Hospital during June 2017. 166 Sputum positive primary TB patients undergoing treatment were included in the study under time-based convenience sampling. Using a self-constructed questionnaire, an interview was conducted of each patient which took about 15 to 20 minutes each. Various demographic factors were determined. The direct and indirect medical costs and income loss was determined. Income per capita and total medical costs were calculated. Data analysis was done on IBM SPSS v23.

Results: The mean total medical cost ranged from Rs.0 to 66,600 with an average of Rs.6371 ± SD rupees. The mean direct medical cost was calculated to be Rs.1095 ± SD that accounted for 18% ± SD of the total medical cost (TMC) and mean indirect medical cost was calculated to be Rs.5250 that accounted for 82% of the TMC. The mean total medical cost is 26% of the mean total family income. TMC was found to be higher in the rural patients as compared to the urban patients ($p < 0.05$). 53% people lost their job because of TB, so had an income loss but those who did not leave their job didn't. Commonly reported coping mechanisms (33.2% people) were money borrowing, selling of assets and leasing of assets. The average income per capita of our subjects was 4765 rupees and 3983 rupees monthly respectively for urban and rural areas, which is almost equal to the national poverty line of 3627 and 3153 rupees monthly income per capita respectively in urban and rural areas. So a mean total monthly medical cost of 6371 rupees due to TB put an extra burden on their budget.

Conclusion: Total medical cost in the TB patients was found to be catastrophic particularly the indirect medical cost. Income loss was reported to be the major contributor to the economic impact. In addition to minimizing the DMC and IMC, there is also a need to develop strategies that could provide financial support to the TB patients.

Keywords: Tuberculosis, TB, Financial burden, Economic Impact, Medical Cost

An estimated 100 million people fall below poverty line because of the economic impact of the disease.² Tuberculosis (TB), which mostly affects the poorest of the poor, is an example of a disease that can substantially contribute to the disease poverty trap.²⁻⁴

Pakistan aims to provide TB diagnosis and

treatment free of charge within the public health services. Access to free TB has expanded substantially over the past two decades through national efforts and global financial support.⁵ Still the TB patients face a number of barriers in seeking diagnosis and treatment including financial costs related to charges for health services, transportation, accom-

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modation, nutrition, lost income and productivity.⁶ These barriers could delay in seeking health care resulting in more advance disease and continued transmission in TB.^{6,7} Direct out of pocket costs for public or private services and indirect opportunity costs can trigger a spiral into deeper poverty for TB patients and their families.⁸

SDGS WHO has developed a post 2015 Global TB program which aims at providing universal social support and financial support to the ill patients⁽⁹⁾. One of the tentative goals for this strategy is “no TB family facing catastrophic costs due to TB”, to be reached by 2035.⁹ TB is a leading cause of death in Pakistan. Based on the incidence cases 2007, WHO ranked Pakistan 7 in the high burden countries.¹⁰ Incidence of TB in Pakistan is 181/100,000 population.¹¹ According to the WHO report 2016, Pakistan is ranked 4th globally in the TB highest burden countries.¹² The recent increase in the Tb is due to the incomplete prior treatment of tuberculosis patients.¹³ Female gender and Ethnic groups at higher risk of developing Tb included Sindhis and Pashtoons.¹³ Other factors responsible for rise in TB include poverty, low awareness, less compliance and suboptimal healthcare infrastructure.^{11,14} This research highlights the major problem faced by the TB patients that is a high economic impact that leads to the non-compliance of the patients which is directly related to the rise in TB so this vicious cycle that develops goes on and on. By assessing the total economic impact on the TB patients we can come forth with different policies to lessen this stress that will ultimately result in a good compliance and at the same time, it will prove helpful in controlling this unrestrainable crises of TB in the long run.

In Pakistan about 62% of the population live in rural areas. The main occupation in the rural areas is agriculture while in the urban areas most people are laborers or self-employed. Transport facilities are much poor in rural areas as compared to urban areas as well as the major health centers which are mostly located in the urban areas. The prevalence of TB in

Pakistan rural areas is more as compared to the urban areas.¹⁵

METHODOLOGY

A cross-sectional study was done in Gulab devi hospital to assess the economic impact in Tb patients. Sputum positive primary pulmonary Tb patients 166 (109 males, 57 females) undergoing treatment in Gulab devi hospital for at least one month were included in the study. Patients of either sex, age group of 15 to onward belonging to any socioeconomic group were included in the study. Patients suffering from the immune suppressive diseases such as AIDS and those suffering from the systemic disorders having symptoms similar to TB were excluded from the study.

Duration of study was 1 month under time based convenience sampling technique. Informed consent was taken verbally. Patients Identity was kept Confidential & only demographic characteristics like age, gender, marital status, education, occupation & address were recorded. Using a self-formulated Questionnaire, an interview was conducted of each patient which took about 15 to 20 minutes. The following information was collected from the sputum positive pulmonary tuberculosis patients: demographic factors, particulars of employment, income of patients and families, expenditure incurred during illness, total family members, income per capita, expenditure per capita and coping mechanisms used by the patients

Medicine costs, hospitalization costs and investigation costs were calculated as direct medical costs endured by the patients. Travelling costs, food costs, attendant income loss and attendant travelling costs were classified as the indirect medical costs. Income loss and income before and after TB was calculated. Loss of income was not calculated for the unemployed patients as they were already dependent on their families before the diagnosis of Tb.

Total cost was calculated by the sum of direct and indirect medical costs and for the income loss patients, loss of income was also added to the total

costs. All costs were calculated in terms of Pakistani rupees.

All the data was entered in the SPSS (Statistical Pack for Social Sciences) Version 20.0

RESULT

A total of 166 patients were included in the study in which 51 patients lived in urban areas, 46 in peri urban and 69 in the rural areas with 109 males and 57 females. The demographic table shows that the 70% males and 67% females belong to the economically productive age group (15 to 45 years).

77% and 61% of males and females had a family size ranging from 4 to 9. 46% of males and 53% of females were found to be illiterate. In the economic tables it can be seen that 61% of the patients (both males and females) had some sort of occupation while the remaining 39% of patients were dependent on their families.

Total medical cost (TMC) ranged from Rs.200 to 66600, with a mean of Rs.6389±sd. Direct medical cost (DMC) ranged from Rs.0 to 10600 with a mean of Rs.1101. Indirect medical cost (IMC) ranged from Rs.0 to 20000 with mean of Rs.4915

Table 1:

Demographic and social characteristics	No. of patients						Total	Total
	Rural 69		Urban 51		Peri-Urban 46		Male %	Female %
	Male N 43	Female N (26)	Male N 40	Female N 11	Male N 26	Female N 20		
Age (years)								
15-25	5(%)	0	12	1	4	0	19	2
26-35	4	3	9	5	5	5	17	22
35-45	17	10	10	5	10	9	34	44
>45	17	13	9	0	7	6	30	33
TOTAL								
Marital Status								
Married	39	25	24	10	22	19	79	95
Non-Married	4	1	16	1	4	1	21	5
Family Size								
1-3	6	6	4	2	2	2	11	18
4-6	15	8	15	1	8	10	39	33
7-9	16	9	16	2	9	5	38	28
>9	6	3	5	6	7	3	12	21
Education								
illiterate	22	20	15	4	13	7	46	54
primary	6	5	7	3	4	11	16	33
secondary	11	0	6	3	4	2	19	8
higher	4	1	12	1	5	0	19	5

Table 2:

Economic characteristics	No. of patients						Total	Total
	Rural		Urban		Peri-Urban		Male %	Female %
	Male n	Female N	Male n	Female n	Male N	Female N		
Occupation								
Jobless	20	8	12	3	11	11	39	39
Job	5	1	13	4	8	2	24	12
Labor	11	1	10	4	2	2	21	12
Business	7	16	5	0	5	5	16	37
Family income (rupees)								
0-20,000	14	12	13	3	4	7	28	39
20,000-40,000	23	13	17	3	18	12	53	49
40,000-60,000	6	1	8	3	3	1	16	9
>60,000	0	0	2	2	1	0	3	3

(table 3).The proportion of IMC to TMC ranged from 0% to 100% with mean of 82% (table 4).The proportion of DMC to TMC ranged from 0 to 100 % with the mean of 18%. The proportion of drug cost to DMC ranged from 0% to 100% with a mean of 18%.The proportion of investigations to DMC ranged from 0 to 100% with a mean of 15%. The proportion of hospitalization cost to DMC ranged from 0 to 100% with a mean of 54%.The proportion of attendant’s travelling cost to IMC ranged from 0 to 55% with a mean of 8%. The proportion of attendant’s income loss to IMC ranged from 0 to 75% with a mean of 14%.The proportion of TMC to family income of the patient ranged from 0 to 103% with a mean of 26%.The proportion of TMC to patient’s income ranged from 0 to 125% with a mean of 50%.

Direct medical cost accounted for 18% of the total medical cost (figure 1). The reason for the low DMC is because the study was conducted in a government hospital where the major contributor to the DMC is the hospitalization cost that accounted for 65% of the total medical cost. TB medicine and investigation is free of cost but the patients have to bear the expenses of medicines and investigations of complications of TB that were approximately found to be 20 and 15% of the total DMC (figure 2). IMC was significantly greater than DMC (p<0.05).

IMC accounted for 82% of the total medical cost in which the major contributor was the food cost 65% (figure 2). IMC was found to be comparatively

high in the patients from the rural areas as compared to the patients from the urban areas because of the patient 15% and attendants 10% transport costs.

Table 4:

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Deviation
direct medical cost	166	.00	10600.00	1101.2048	1462.26217
indirect medical cost	166	.00	20000.00	4915.0602	3210.69458
TMC	166	200.00	66600.00	6389.7590	5952.40089
Valid N (listwise)	166				

Figure: 1

Figure: 2

Table 3:

Statistics											
	Proportion DMC / TMC	Proportion attendant income cost/IMC	Proportion attendant travel cost/IMC	Proportion transportation / IMC	Proportion hospitalization /DMC	Proportion investigation/DMC	Proportion TMC/ INCOME	Proportion medicine/ DMC	Proportion food/IMC	Proportion IMC/ TMC	
N	Valid	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		17.8189	13.8314	8.4268	9.5125	63.40	15.90	26.5490	20.00	64.4295	81.6510
Median		13.0435	.0000	5.6080	.0000	60.0000	.0000	22.6970	.0000	67.4242	86.9209
Std. Deviation		16.26641	20.73863	11.06357	19.23335	42.77443	29.44100	19.81698	31.74939	28.86975	17.46539
Range		100.00	75.00	54.55	100.00	100.00	100.00	103.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Minimum		.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
Maximum		100.00	75.00	54.55	100.00	100.00	100.00	103.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Figure: 3

111 people (66.8%) didn't have any coping mechanism, 38 people (22.8%) borrowed money, 14 people (8.4%) sold their assets and 3 people (1.8%) leased their assets. There was a significant difference between people who had coping mechanisms and those who didn't ($p < 0.05$, $CI = 95\%$). The most common monetary measure to cope with Tb in the patients was found to be money borrowing (22.8%). Only a fraction (10.2%) of patients with the major complications of the TB had to sell and lease their assets in order to meet their expenses.

In 79 patients (47.5%) the income loss was found to be insignificant. 37 of the patients bear the high income loss ranging from Rs.15,000 to 20,000 while 28% have an income loss between Rs.10,000 to 15,000. 26 patients (22.2%) have an income loss of Rs.10,000 to 15,000 and 3 people (1.8%) have an income loss greater than Rs.20,000.

Figure 4

53% (30.3% urban, 31.4% peri-urban and

38.2% rural) of the total subjects in our study had an average income loss 10562 rupees along with the 6552 rupees of TMC burden so they had an economic impact of a total Rs.17114 while the other 47% had a burden of about Rs.6372 due to the DMC and IMC only. It clearly depicts that the income loss is a major contributor in the economic impact on the TB patients.

Figure: 5

In table 5 the mean direct cost for urban, peri-urban and rural patients were calculated to be 1011, 971 and 1253 rupees and median Rs.600. The mean indirect costs were 4456, 4939 and 6490 rupees and median (Rs.3500, 4400 and 5000) respectively for the 3 regions. Total costs were calculated as Rs.5468, 5910 and 6490 and median (Rs.4100, 5000 and 5600) respectively for the 3 regions. Thus the most socioeconomic impact was faced by the patients from the rural areas as max. total costs were incurred by them.

In figure 4 direct costs are compared with the indirect costs among the 166 patients from the rural, urban and peri urban area. Indirect costs were Rs.4456, Rs.4939 and Rs.5237 respectively in the urban, peri-urban and rural patients and direct medical costs were calculated to be Rs.1011, Rs.971 and Rs.1253 respectively in the patients from the following 3 regions. While indirect costs were higher in the patients from the 3 areas, both costs were higher among the rural patients.

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In figure 5 total medical cost has been compared with the income per capita of the urban, peri urban and rural patients. The mean income per capita of the three regions is 4765, 4065 and 3983 rupees respectively while the mean TMC total medical cost

Table 5:

Region		Direct costs Rupees	Indirect costs Rupees	Total costs Rupees
Urban	Mean	1011	4456	5468
	Median	600	3500	4100
	Range	0-8000	0-20000	0-2800
Peri-urban	Mean	971	4939	5910
	Median	600	4400	5000
	Range	0-6000	1000-10000	1000-16000
Rural	Mean	1253	5237	6490
	Median	600	5000	5600
	Range	0-10600	0-20000	0-30600

Figure: 6

is 5468, 5910 and 6490 rupees, from which it is clearly evident that the income per capita is lowest in the rural patients and the total medical cost confronted by them is the highest among the 3 of them. It clearly depicts that the economic impact or socioeconomic impact of TB in the rural patients is towering.

Total mean family income is 28451 rupees with the mean family incomes of the urban, peri urban and rural patients were calculated to be 33036, 27752 and 24565 rupees respectively. The proportion of TMC to mean family income in urban, peri urban and rural patients were calculated to be 14.42, 14.64 and 16.21. Thus the highest burden of TMC was

Figure 7

found to be on the total family income of the rural patients as compared to the families of urban and peri urban areas.

There is a significant association between total medical cost and the address of the patient on Chi-Square test ($p < 0.05$).

Figure: 8

In our study Tb was found to be prevalent in the illiterate of our society (46% males and 53%). It was mostly because of the lack of awareness about the TB treatment and its spread. There is a significant association between education and TMC on Chi-Square test ($p < 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

This study demonstrates the economic burden of seeking TB care is very high for patients and their families. TB is one of the most prevalent diseases in Pakistan and its treatment comes with a high risk of financial ruin for many patients. Economic impact-

Table : 6

Address – TMC Association								
			TMC					Total
			0-3000	3001-6000	6001-9000	9001-12000	12001-999999	
Address	urban	Count	15	22	4	6	4	51
		% within address	29.4%	43.1%	7.8%	11.8%	7.8%	100.0%
	peri urban	Count	6	20	16	4	0	46
		% within address	13.0%	43.5%	34.8%	8.7%	0.0%	100.0%
	rural	Count	12	23	17	11	6	69
		% within address	17.4%	33.3%	24.6%	15.9%	8.7%	100.0%
Total		Count	33	65	37	21	10	166
		% within address	19.9%	39.2%	22.3%	12.7%	6.0%	100.0%

Table : 7

Education – TMC Association								
			TMC					Total
			0-3000	3001-6000	6001-9000	9001-12000	12001-999999	
Education	illiterate	Count	21	37	16	5	2	81
		% within education	25.9%	45.7%	19.8%	6.2%	2.5%	100.0%
	primary	Count	1	13	10	9	3	36
		% within education	2.8%	36.1%	27.8%	25.0%	8.3%	100.0%
	secondary	Count	2	8	8	5	3	26
		% within education	7.7%	30.8%	30.8%	19.2%	11.5%	100.0%
	higher	Count	9	7	3	2	2	23
		% within education	39.1%	30.4%	13.0%	8.7%	8.7%	100.0%
Total		Count	33	65	37	21	10	166
		% within education	19.9%	39.2%	22.3%	12.7%	6.0%	100.0%

varies in the patients of rural, peri urban and urban areas.

The present study has documented all the costs incurred by the TB patients undergoing treatment. Similar studies had been conducted in India and Bangladesh in our region where the financial losses in the TB patients had been calculated.^{16,17} In Pakistan no such extensive study has been done (limited reliable published) related to the economic impact on Tb patients except one study in which only the treatment cost and income loss were calculated leaving the indirect medical costs while most of the other studies, done on Tb are related to its awareness and prevalence.¹⁸

Economic impact was assessed by calculating the DMC which included the medicine, investigation and hospitalization costs. Indirect medical cost which included travelling costs, food costs, attendants income loss and attendants travelling costs was found to be more burden in TB patients as compared

to the DMC because most of the medical care except for the comorbidities, was free of cost for the TB patient as the study was conducted in the government hospital. The major economic impact proved to be the income loss. It is well known that adults aged 15 to 59 years are the most economically productive individuals; they are also the individuals on whom the other family members are dependent thus TB in these patients impede the development of society.^{17,19} In our study about 70% of the patients were aged between 15 to 45 years which clearly depicts that TB has most of its impact on the productive adults.

In this study the sampling was done to include patients from either sex (male 65% and females 35%) undergoing treatment of TB in ghulab devi hospital.(similar to other studies)

The total mean direct cost observed in our studies was calculated to be Rs.1095±sd. Despite the free treatment of TB in Gulab Devi hospital patients still have to pay for the hospitalization cost and for

the medicines and investigations of the comorbidities of TB. Most of the patients suffering from TB had multiple complications for which they had to buy medicine out of their own pocket. Total mean DMC was found to be lower as compared to the 1500 to 2000 rupees of total mean DMC incurred by the patients in India and south Punjab of Pakistan.^{16,18}

Indirect medical costs (costs incurred in travel, food and attendant's expenditures) were the expenditures incurred by the patients that imposed a great deal of burden on them. Mean indirect medical cost was calculated to be Rs.5250 which is about 5 times in comparison to the DMC. Although the special diet (mutton) was provided to the patient 3 times a day, still they had to buy fruits and other eatables on their own that accounted for 65% of the IMC. In addition to food many patients had to bear high transport cost (15% of the IMC) especially those patients who had to visit the hospital on and off for their treatment. Attendant's income loss and travel cost also contributed to about 20% of the IMC. The IMC was found greater than the mean IMC of US14\$ incurred by the patients in Zambia (20). Non-medical expenditures were also found to be greater in our study as compared to the patients in India.¹⁶

DMC and IMC both were found to be higher in the rural patients as compared to the urban patient as they had to travel to the urban areas to get treated because of the unavailability of a proper TB care center in the rural areas.

Income loss is a major setback for the TB patients especially for those patients who are the sole bread earners of the families. In our study 53 % of the patients interviewed and questioned bear heavy income loss (mean Rs.10562) due to TB which significantly reduced the total family income and they were dependent on their family members. Other 48% of the patients who didn't have the income loss bear only a loss of mean 6732 rupees as compared to the 17112 rupees of heavy money loss.

Mean total medical was calculated to be 6371 rupees which consist of 18% of the DMC and 82% of the IMC. Mean TMC was also high in rural patients

compared to the urban patients (table 2). Mean total medical cost was also more than the Rs.2700 of TMC incurred by the TB patients in India. Mean of the total family income was 28450 rupees with mean income higher in urban areas as compared to rural areas and burden of TMC on the mean total family income was calculated to be approximately 26% and burden of TMC on mean patients individual income was about 50% which has led the patients in to money borrowing (23%) and selling and leasing of assets (11%).

According to a survey the poverty line in Pakistan is drawn at 3627 and 3153 rupees (income per capita)¹ respectively in both the urban and rural areas while the patients inducted in our study had an income per capita of 4765 rupees and 3983 rupees respectively for both the urban and rural areas. So most of our patient were already at the borderline of the poverty and were already hand to mouth. So a mean total medical cost of 6371 rupees due to TB plus the income loss put an immense economic impact on them.

CONCLUSION

TB is a serious health issue in Pakistan. According to 2017-18 health budget policy of Pakistan (link given below), 124 million rupees²¹ has been allocated for the National TB control program which is a good initiative but sadly it is not enough due to the increasing TB expenditures. Government needs to build TB control centers in rural areas so that the rural patient can be facilitated and the alarming patient burden in the urban hospitals can decline. In addition to minimizing the DMC and IMC, government also need to come up with a plan to provide financial support to the TB patients.

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